

- DEMO_FAS_Funktion
- View All
- Hide/Show Model Browser
- Fit to DEMO_FAS
- Zoom MO_FAS
- Subsystem
- DEMO_FAS
- DEMO_FAS Funktion

DEMO_FAS_Funktion		
-Main		
Name	Value	
ShowPortLabels	FromPc	
Permissions	ReadW	
ErrorFen		
PermitHierarchicalResolution	All	
TreatAsAtomicUnit	off	
TreatAsGroupedWhenPropagatingVariantConditions		
+Other		

- Hide/Show Model Browser